

AGE AND GENDER DEPENDENCE OF WOOL PRODUCTIVITY OF CAMELS

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Summary. The article given information about the productivity of wool and its composition in camels of different ages and sexes, as well as the dependence of the vegetation cover on the productivity of wool.

Key words: camel, age periods, wool productivity, wool composition, vegetation cover.

Introduction. Camel breeding is a branch of animal husbandry that deals with the breeding and use of camels. Camel breeding developed in desert, semi-desert and dry steppe regions. Dromedary (one-humped) camels adapted to a warm climate live in the southern regions of Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Afghanistan, India, Iran, Turkey and African countries, cold-resistant Bactrian (double-humped) camels live in the northern part of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, the Astrakhan region of Russia, and the Kalmyk deserts, Tuva, Altai Territory, Mongolia, are grown and used in the western regions of China.

The camel's thick and long wool protects it from the sun in the heat and from the cold in the bitter cold. Camel hair is sheared in the spring, and 75% is tweed. Carpets are woven from camel wool, and wool raw materials are also widely used in textiles. Clothes made of camel wool are important because they protect and heal the body from cold.

Changes in the quantity and quality of wool productivity in the age dynamics of two-humped camels mainly depend on their storage technology, feeding methods and productivity of pasture plants. Therefore, in terms of increasing the wool productivity of camels, it is an urgent issue to study the wool productivity and its composition in terms of their age and regions.

Research methods. The researches were conducted in "Ata-Mura" and "Konratli Aqniet" farms specializing in camel breeding, belonging to Ustyurt OFY, Qungirotdistrict of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Determination of wool productivity of camels was carried out during the spring shearing period (in May), and the amount of sheared wool (in grams) was measured on a platform scale (accuracy of ± 5 grams) and divided into 4th class. According to the analysis results, efficient methods for selection and sorting of two-humped camels were developed.

According to the morphology of wool, the amount of wool was taken from different body parts of a certain number of camels, and the amount of coarse wool, intermediate wool and tweed wool was determined and expressed in percentages.

Wool coefficient (Patent No. 2007/144.31. 27.11. 2007) was determined based on the following formula.

$$\text{KNS} = \frac{\text{NS}}{\text{JM}} \times 100$$

Here, KNS is the wool shear coefficient

NS- Wool shearing

JM- live weight

Research results. The wool productivity of camels of different ages was studied in the research, and the amount of fleece and wool in the wool was also determined. In our research, wool productivity was measured in spring shearing and these values are presented in Table 1 below.

The analysis of table data shows that there were differences in the parameters of wool shearing in the age and sex section of camels, and in the sex section of camels. 18-month-old young male camels were 3.76 ± 0.21 kg in terms of wool, while this indicator was equal to 3.38 ± 0.19 kg in female young camels. In the dynamics of age, it was 4.66 ± 0.28 and 4.38 ± 0.24 kg, respectively, at 42 months. At 18 months, the differences were 380 grams, and at 42 months, the difference between the sexes in wool content was 400 grams.

Table 1

Wool shearing parameters of camels age and gender

Age of camels	Gender	Head count	Forty		From this:			
			kg	%, ±	Runo, kg	%	Mileage, kg	%
			X±Sx		X±Sx		X±Sx	
18 months old	♂	4	3,76±0,21	100	3,21±0,23	85,3	0,55±0,05	14,6
	♀	7	3,38±0,19	100	3,06±0,16	92,6	0,32±0,02	9,4
30 months old	♂	6	4,39±0,25	+0,6	3,71±0,21	84,5	0,68±0,06	15,5
	♀	8	3,85±0,25	+0,5	3,43±0,21	89,1	0,42±0,04	10,9
42 months old	♂	5	4,66±0,28	+0,9	3,91±0,23	83,9	0,75±0,05	16,9
	♀	7	4,38±0,24	+1,0	3,88±0,28	88,6	0,50±0,03	11,4
By average age	♂	15	4,27±0,34	+0,5	3,61±2,97	84,5	0,66±0,06	15,5
	♀	22	3,87±0,23	+0,5	3,46±3,09	89,4	0,41±0,03	10,6

There are differences between sexes in the amount of wool shearing of camels, and the age dynamics of these indicators is preserved. The main valuable piece of wool is runo wool. There are differences in fleece yield, age and sex of camels. Male camels accounted for 85.3% of the total wool sheared during the 18-month period, while female camels accounted for 92.6%, i.e. 7.3% prevailed.

By the age of 42 months, such differences were equal to 4.7%. In conclusion, it can be said that the amount of tivit wool predominates in young females, and this indicator decreases with age. Yolo wool is among the low-value wools obtained from these camels, and the difference in age of these wools is shown in picture 1.

Picture 1. Indicators of changes in wool of camels by age and gender.

From the data of picture 1, it is known that the amount of wool increases due to the low amount of tivit wool in male bushes. In the period of 18 months, the amount of shorn wool was 14.6% in male flocks, while in female flocks this indicator was 9.4% and decreased by 5.2%. During the period of 42 months, the amount of sheared wool was equal to 16.9 and 11.4%, respectively, in the jinn section, that is, the differences remained at 5.5%.

waist section neck section abdomen lateral section

Picture 2. Tivit wool samples taken from different places of camels

The amount of wool sheared by camels is estimated to some extent by their pure wool yield. The yield of clean wool in our experimental work is shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2

Wool yield indicators, %, number of samples taken, n=5

Indicators	Gender	Age of camels			By average age
		18 months	30 months	42 months	
		X± Sx			
Amount of sheared wool, kg	♂	3,76±0,21	4,39±0,25	4,66±0,28	4,27±0,34
	♀	3,38±0,19	3,85±0,25	4,38±0,24	3,87±0,23
Amount of pure wool, kg	♂	3,33±0,28	3,92±0,37	4,25±0,40	3,83±0,32
	♀	2,94±0,25	3,40±0,31	3,96±2,98	3,43±0,29
%	♂	88,6	89,4	91,3	89,8
	♀	87,1	88,4	90,6	88,7

The analysis of the table data shows that differences can be seen in the obtained data on the yield of pure wool in terms of age and sex of camels. The yield of pure wool was 88.6% in wool samples taken from young male camels at 18 months of age, and 87.1% in wool samples taken from female camels. Such differences are 89.4% at 30 months and 42 months, respectively; 88.4%; and made 91.3% and 90.6%.

In conclusion, it can be said that as the age of camels increased, their pure wool output increased due to the increase in wool, and on the contrary, the high amount of tivit wool led to a decrease in this pure wool output.

According to the data presented in Table 3, according to the dependence of wool productivity of camels on the areas of their storage, 5 pasture districts belonging to the Ustyurt plateau were taken, and the wool productivity of two-humped camels between the ages of 18 and 42 months kept in them was determined. According to these data, wool productivity of camels sheared from Dautata district is assumed to be 100%, it was found that the amount of wool in the northern part of Ustyurt is higher by +3.3% in the deep plain district, by +11.4% in the Central Middle Ustyurt deep plain district, and vice versa, the following In the central district of the Ustyurt plateau, -4.3% and -9.4% less indicators were obtained in the Qoshbulok district.

Table 3

Dependence of wool productivity of camels on their storage areas (between 18 months and 42 months, kg)

Usturt areas	The number of camels that have been slaughtered	Forty, kg	
		X± Sx	%, ±
Dautata region	15	4,27±0,31	100
The northern part of Ustyurt deep plain district	13	4,41±0,38	+3,3
Central district of the Ustyurt plateau	11	4,09±0,34	-4,3
Qoshbulok region	7	3,87±0,22	-9,4
Central Middle Ustyurt depth district	11	4,76±0,42	+11,4
Average on the Ustyurt plateau	57	4,39±0,25	+2,8

These indicators indicate that pasture conditions can be proved by how high the productivity and density of plant flora is. In the Central Middle Ustyurt depth district, it was found that there was an increase in the amount of wool by +11.4%. Sarikamish lake is located in this district, and the surrounding area of the lake is distinguished by its rich flora, which in turn affects the productivity of camels.

Conclusion. It was observed that wool productivity increased with the age of male and female camels from 18 to 42 months of age. At the same time, an increase in the amount of pure wool was observed with increasing age. Depending on the regions, it was found that the wool productivity of camels is higher in the Central Middle Ustyurt depth district due to the vegetation cover and productivity of the pastures.

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